

UNUSUAL PRESENTATION OF A MECKEL'S DIVERTICULUM: A CASE REPORT

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INTRODUCTION

The most prevalent congenital gastrointestinal tract malformation, known as Meckel's diverticulum (MD), results from partial obliteration of the proximal portion of the omphalomesenteric duct during the seventh week of pregnancy [1]. The "rule of twos" has been used to describe this congenital anomaly, which is typically found two feet proximal to the ileocecal valve, present before the age of two, twice as common in men as in women, and affects 2% of the population [2]. With all of the small bowel wall's layers contained within, it is the only real diverticulum in the small intestine. Clinically speaking, MD is largely silent, especially in adults. Male sex, age less than 50, the existence of a diverticulum 2 cm or longer in length, or those containing heterotopic mucosa are among the risk factors known to develop symptomatic MD [3].

According to reference [4], the percentage of symptomatic MD rose to 25, 42, and 70% when two, three, or four of these criteria were satisfied.

A fibrous attachment to the abdominal wall was also mentioned by Robijn et al. as a risk factor [5].

The most frequent presenting symptom in the adult population is some form of intestinal obstruction. Giant MD cases (>5 cm) are comparatively uncommon and are linked to more serious complications, particularly when there is blockage [6, 7]. A very uncommon consequence of MD is axial torsion and gangrene [8,9]. Approximately 60% of Meckel's diverticula contain heterotopic mucosa, of which over 60% consist of gastric mucosa [3,4]. Other pancreatic mucosa (5%) and less commonly colonic mucosa, endometriosis, hepatobiliary tissue, which are responsible for other complications like hemorrhage, chronic peptic ulceration and perforation.

CASE REPORT

An 18-year-old male presented to the emergency department with abdominal pain, distension and oral intolerance. He complained of peri-umbilical pain and nausea since 3 days which progressively worsened in the last 24 h and worsening of symptoms of perforated peritonitis with high grade fever. He had no relevant medical history or previous surgery. Family history was unremarkable.

On physical examination, he was febrile (38.5 °C) and hemodynamically stable (blood pressure 127/83 mmHg, heart rate 110 beats/min, SpO₂ 98%). The abdomen was distended and bowel sounds were absent. There was severe tenderness to palpation on the all quadrants, mainly in the midline, but with rigidity or guarding. No abdominal scars or hernias were present. Rectal examination was negative.

Laboratory testing revealed leukocytosis with neutrophilia and elevated C-reactive protein.

Upright chest plain radiography shows evidence of free gas under right dome of diaphragm.

Figure 1 Chest X-ray - free gas under right dome of diaphragm

Hollow viscus perforation was suggested as a cause. He was taken up for emergent laparotomy. On exploration findings included there is evidence of perforation on meckel's diverticulum 60 cm away from IC junction. We performed excision of meckel's diverticulum with resection and anastomosis done. Histology revealed small bowel with necrotic lesions and gangrenous MD. The recovery was uneventful. The patient was discharged within 10 days. At 6-month follow-up the patient was well and remained asymptomatic.

Figure 2 showing perforated segment of meckels diverticulum

Figure 3 showing resection and anastomosis done

DISCUSSION

In large series, documented incidences of symptomatic MD range from 4% to 16% [3,4,11,12]. A retrospective study involving 1476 patients from the Mayo Clinic found that among other characteristics, diverticulum length longer than 2 cm was linked to symptoms in 16% of all MD patients [4].

In adults, intestinal obstruction accounts for 40% of symptomatic cases, making it the most common presentation. With MD serving as the leading point, intussusception—a mechanical volvulus of the small intestine centered around a persistent fibrous band that connects the MD to the umbilicus—is the most frequent cause of obstruction [8]. This is followed by GI bleed and lastly, diverticulitis [3,4]. Some studies estimate the incidence of diverticulitis to be 20% of symptomatic cases [5,9]. Spontaneous perforation due to diverticulitis is even less common [10,11]. A study by Chen et al. concerning the behavior of MD in children showed only 7.3% of symptomatic MD was perforated [15]. Meanwhile, the Mayo Clinic reported 10–12% of symptomatic patients with perforation

As in our case, the perforated MD may be leading to episodes of peritonitis.

An uncommon consequence is axial twisting of MD around its narrow base. Furthermore, axial torsion-related gangrene of MD is an incredibly uncommon occurrence [8,9]. An essential predisposition factor is the anatomical configuration, particularly the diverticular length and base diameter [3,7-9]. Torsion is much more likely to occur in an elongated variant with a narrowed neck [7], while foreign body entrapment can occur in short, large-base diverticula [13]. The diverticulum in our instance was 10 cm long and 2 cm wide, which might have made it more prone to torsion. Its narrow base experienced axial torsion, which reduced blood flow and caused gangrene.

Preoperative diagnosis accounts for less than 10% of adult cases of complicated MD [13–15]. It can be challenging to accurately diagnose complicated MD prior to surgery because there are several intra-abdominal conditions that can mimic its symptoms, including appendicitis, inflammatory bowel disease, or various reasons why small bowel obstruction occurs [12]. In particular, accurate for patients who don't just have bleeding symptoms.

88% of patients who presented with bleeding in a study of 776 patients had the proper preoperative diagnosis, compared to 11% of patients with indications other than hemorrhage [16].

In most cases, plain radiographs are not useful in diagnosing MD. However, small bowel obstruction and perforation is usually visible on plain films of the abdomen. In simple cases, it can be challenging to differentiate MD on CT from the normal small bowel [2].

Despite the increased use of CT for abdomen imaging, the way MD appears on traditional CT depends on the complication that led to the patient's presentation. Poorer diagnostic acuity was linked to the presence of gangrene or secondary small bowel obstruction in a report of CT findings in 11 patients with Meckel's diverticulitis. Administration of both intravenous and oral contrast material may help establish the diagnosis of Meckel's diverticulitis and should be administered whenever possible [17].

Lastly, reports of laparoscopy as a diagnostic technique in symptomatic MD cases have also been made [18].

Around 6% of symptomatic patients die, and this number rises in older patients who have complications [11, 18–20]. There is a considerable risk of morbidity and mortality if a complex MD is not diagnosed promptly [9].

The standard of care for symptomatic MD patients is surgical resection.

Simple diverticulectomy or ileal resection are two possible surgical procedures.

When there is proof of a tumor, perforation, or severe inflammation, the later procedure is recommended [4]. Skilled surgeons can perform laparoscopic procedures without a higher risk of complications [18]. It is necessary to remove any related attachments to the abdominal wall. Early postoperative complications have a cumulative incidence of 12%, with a 1.5% mortality rate. The most common complications are surgical site infection (3%), prolonged ileus (3%) and anastomotic leak (2%).

CONCLUSION

The difficulty in treating adults with symptomatic MD is in getting a timely surgical diagnosis and treatment. Because of its rarity, high index suspicion is required because the clinical presentation can vary, differential diagnosis can be challenging, and imaging methods might not be helpful. It is uncommon for young adults with hollow viscus perforation to have a diagnosis prior to surgery. It is advised to undergo a CT scan with oral and intravenous contrast (if feasible) to get past these challenges. In our instance, we have discovered several

risk factors in retrospect that ought to have been recognized earlier to avoid postponing surgical intervention. Patients with unusual presentations should have their MD's complications in mind.

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